

Research Article

Production of Bioethanol from waste newspaper using Yeast isolate from Palm oil polluted soil

Ifeanyichukwu Edeh* and Obinna Ezeibe

Department of Chemical Engineering,
University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

*Email of the Corresponding author: ifeanyichukwu.edeh@uniport.edu.ng

[Received 21 Feb-2023, Revised 20 March-2023, Accepted 26 March-2023, Published 31 March-2023]

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7820991

Abstract

Bioethanol is currently being produced in commercial quantity in most countries of the world using edible feedstocks such as maize, sugarcane and wheat. Unfortunately, this contributes up to 85 % of the production cost making bioethanol more expensive than gasoline. The current work, investigates the potential of using waste newspaper as a feedstock and yeast isolate from palm oil polluted soil for bioethanol production. This was carried out by Separate Hydrolysis and Fermentation method (SHF) using yeast isolate extracted from palm oil impacted soil. The result of the proximate analysis of the waste newspaper revealed a high carbohydrate content of 80.2 %, the biochemical characteristics of the yeast isolate shows positive to the fermentation of most of the reducing sugars such as lactose, sucrose, galactose and glucose. The pH was varied from 6 - 8.5 while keeping other parameters constant, the result gave a maximum bioethanol concentration of 0.246 mg/mL and yeast biomass of 0.64 mg/mL using pH 7 after inoculation time of 8 days. The inoculum size was varied between 2 and 10 % at constant pH, and temperature. The result shows that the maximum bioethanol (0.27 mg/mL) and yeast biomass (0.60 mg/mL) were obtained using an inoculum size of 6 % after 8 days of incubation. The yeast isolate (pops 1) using MSM, 25 % waste newspaper and 2 % corn steep liquor gave the highest concentration of bioethanol of 24.2 mg/mL after 14 days of fermentation. Being that the feedstock and yeast source are waste, it is expected that the cost of production of ethanol will be reduced, and the use of the waste newspaper as a feedstock is a valorization and sustainable waste management strategies.

Keywords: Bioethanol; yeast; waste newspaper; fermentation; Biofuel; yeast isolate

1.0 Introduction

Due to the continuous utilization of fossil fuels as the major source of energy in the world, there is a global outcry in view of its suspected depletion and the attendant cause of climate change. To address this problem, researchers

all over the world are working on alternative energy sources which are renewable and environmentally friendly. Biofuels such as bioethanol possesses such quality and is currently being used in countries like the

United States and Brazil to complement the conventional gasoline. Although, the greatest challenge is the high cost of feedstock as about 60 %, 25 %, and 3 % of the bioethanol globally are produced from maize, sugarcane, and wheat and respectively with United States leading in 2021 with 1,435.8 petajoules production [14]. Most of these feedstocks are edible and their use in bioethanol production currently competes with other uses such as human consumption and utilization in the chemical industries. In Nigeria, bioethanol production is still at its nascent stage, especially as the policy on blending 90 % gasoline with 10 % bioethanol through importation of biofuel and achieving 100 % of in-country biofuel production by 2020, is yet to be actualized [1]. In the contemporary time, the use of waste feedstocks in bioethanol production is being investigated. For instance, waste paper is currently being considered a cheap raw material for the production of bioethanol since it is readily available and renewable [5]. The waste paper generation is greater than 400 million tones per annum [18]. At the moment, waste paper is being managed by disposing it into the landfills or incineration which are known to be environmentally unfriendly as a result of the emission of greenhouse gases and leachate contamination [17,23]. The utilization of waste paper in bioethanol production lends itself in mitigation of climate change and as an efficient strategy for the management of municipal waste papers [7]. Bioethanol is produced by the fermentation of reducing sugars obtained from hydrolysis of carbohydrate by microorganisms. Microorganisms like yeasts are quite essential in the fermentation of reducing sugars such as glucose, galactose, and hexose to bioethanol. This is because of high yield of ethanol (>90% theoretical yield), ethanol tolerance of more than 40 g/L, ethanol productivity of greater than 1.0 g/L, ability to grow in a simple, cheap media and undiluted fermentation broth which poses a resistance to inhibitors and slow down the growth of contaminants [6,10]. The current work assesses the potential of yeast isolates

from palm oil polluted soil in bioethanol production using waste papers as feedstock. The effect of process parameters such as pH, time, inoculum size and carbon: nitrogen and nutrients combination on bioethanol and yeast biomass production were evaluated. The physicochemical properties of the bioethanol produced were analysed in order to determine its suitability for use as potential replacement or complement for the conventional gasoline.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Sample collection

The soil samples were obtained from two major palm oil mills in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. The waste newspapers were old Guardian Newspaper publications obtained from Newspaper archives in a private residence in Rumuodomaya, Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria

2.1.2 Chemicals

DinitroSalicylic acid also known as DNS, Sulfuric acid (98% pure, LOBACHEMIE product), Sodium hydroxide (97% pure, MOLYCHEM product), Sterile normal saline (0.9% - 9g of salt per litre), Sodium sulphate (99% pure, Guangdong Chemical Reagent Engineering-technological Research and Development Center Product), Potassium sulphate (99% pure, Guangdong Chemical Reagent Engineering-technological Research and Development Center Product), Potassium Iodide (99% pure, SURECHEM Products Ltd, bought from JOECHEM Chemicals), Potassium dichromate (99% pure, KERMEL Products), Iodine (98% pure), Calcium alginate gel, mercuric oxide, Petroleum ether, Hydrochloric acid, Paraffin wax. The Mineral Salt media used was Bushnell Haas Broth (T.M MEDIA Product), Glucose Yeast Peptone media used was Potato Dextrose Agar. All these chemicals were purchased from JOECHEM Chemicals, Rivers State, Nigeria. The Chloramphenicol (antibiotics) and Corn kernel were purchased from CAPPINO

Company and local market in Alakahia, respectively).

2.1.3 Equipment/apparatuses

G & G Analytical Weighing Machine (JJ300 Model), Stainless Steel Portable Pressure Sterilizer (YX-280A Model), Thermostat Oven (DHG-9023A Model), B-Bran Microscope (XSZ-107BN Model), Thermostat Incubator (DNP-9022-1A Model), pH meter (HANNA Instruments with range 0.0 to 14.0 pH and resolution 0.1 pH), and Vacuum pump and Buchner funnel/flask

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Proximate compositional analysis of waste newspaper

(1). Moisture Content

10 g of previously ground waste newspaper sample was dried in the oven at 105 °C for 12 hr, and then allowed to cool to the ambient temperature before weighing to determine the final weight. The moisture content of the sample was determined using Equation 1.

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = 100 \times \frac{(B-A)-(C-A)}{(B-A)} \quad (1)$$

Where: A= weight of empty weighing pan(g); B= weight of weighing pan + wet sample(g) and C= weight of weighing pan + dry sample(g)

(2). Crude Protein

3mL of the waste newspaper sample was weighed into the kjeldahl flask, and 10 g of potassium sulphate, 0.7 g mercuric oxide and 20mL concentrated sulphuric acid were added respectively. The flask was placed tilted at an angle in the digester and heated until the solution began to boil and was clear. It was further heated for about 30mins before a paraffin wax was added to reduce the foam. The sample was allowed to cool as 90mL distilled, de-ionized water was added gradually. Upon cooling, 25mL of sodium sulphate solution was added and stirred. One glass bead and 80mL of 40% sodium hydroxide solution were added while the flask was kept tilted leading to the formation of two layers. The flask was quickly

connected to the distillation unit, heated and 50mL of distillate containing ammonia in 50mL of indicator solution was collected at the end of the distillation, the receptor flask was removed and the end of the condenser rinsed and the solution titrated with a standard hydrochloric acid solution. The crude protein content was determined using Equation 3.2.

$$\text{Nitrogen in sample (\%)} = \frac{100(A \times 0.0142)}{C} \quad (2)$$

Crude protein (%) = nitrogen in sample x 6.25

Where: A= hydrochloric acid used in titration (ml); B= normality of standard acid; C= weight of sample (g)

(3). Crude Lipids

The extraction flask was removed from the kiln after heating using tongs, cooled and weighed. 5 g of dry sample was weighed into an extraction thimble and was transferred to the extraction unit using tongs. The flask containing petroleum ether at 2/3 of total volume was connected to the extractor. The sample was boiled and the heat adjusted to obtain 10 refluxes per hour. The ether was then evaporated by distillation. The flasks were placed in a dryer and weighed to within milligrams. The crude lipids content was determined using Equation 3.

$$\text{Crude lipids content (\%)} = 100 \times \frac{(B-A)}{C} \quad (3)$$

Where: A= weight of clean dry flask (g); B= weight of flask with fat (g); C= weight of sample (g).

(4). Ash

5 g of dry sample was placed in a crucible previously calcinated and brought to constant weight. The crucible was placed in the furnace and heated at 550°C for 12 hours after which it was allowed to cool, and thereafter transferred to a dryer. The crucible containing the ash was carefully weighed again. The ash content was determined using Equation 4.

$$\text{Ash content (\%)} = 100 \times \frac{(A-B)}{C} \quad (4)$$

Where: A= weight of crucible with sample (g);
B= weight of crucible with ash (g); C= weight of sample

(5) Crude fibre

3 g of defatted, dry sample was placed in the flask and 200 mL boiling sulphuric acid solution was added. The condenser was attached and brought to the boiling point in 1 min, and antiform was added where necessary. The mixture was boiled for exactly 30 min, maintaining the volume of distilled water constant and swirling the flask periodically to remove particles adhering to the sides. Buchner funnel was lined with the filter paper and pre-heated with boiling water. After boiling for 30 mins, the flask was removed and allowed to cool for 1 min. The contents were thereafter filtered carefully for 10min, using suction. The filter paper was then washed with boiling water and the residue transferred to the flask using a retort containing 200 mL of boiling NaOH solution, and boiled for 30 min. The filtration crucible was pre-heated with boiling water and the hydrolysed mixture was carefully filtered after allowing it to cool for 1 min. The residue was then washed with boiling water, HCl solution and then again with boiling water. The final washing was done with petroleum ether. The crucible was the placed in a kiln set at 105°C for 12 hr and then cooled. The crucible was quickly weighed with the residue inside and placed in the crucible furnace at 550°C for 3 hr. It was left to cool in a desiccator and re-weighed. The crude fibre content was determined using Equation 5.

$$\text{Crude fibre content (\%)} = 100 \times \frac{A-B}{C} \quad (5)$$

Where: A= weight of crucible with sample (g);
B= weight of crucible with crude fibre (g); C= weight of sample (g)

(6) . Carbohydrate content

The carbohydrate content was obtained using Equation (6)

$$\% \text{ Carbohydrate} = (100 - \% (\text{Moisture} + \text{Crude protein} + \text{Crude lipid} + \text{Ash} + \text{Crude fibre})) \quad (6)$$

2.2.2. Enrichment of palm oil polluted soil samples

The soil samples were enriched in Mineral salt media (Bushnell Haas media-BHM) using palm oil from the study location as carbon source. 90mL of the Bushnell Hass media was distributed in 250mL conical flask and supplemented with 10 mL of palm oil and sterilization was monitored at 121°C and 15 psi for 15 min. The palm oil was further sterilized by Vacuum filtration, then the setup was aerated and agitated using an orbital shaker incubator (Stuart, Germany S150) at 170 RPM and 37°C for 30 min [8].

2.2.3 Isolation of yeast species from palm oil polluted soil

The enriched soil samples, mineral salt medium and palm oil were diluted using 9.9 mL sterile normal saline. Glucose yeast peptone media was prepared and autoclaved at 121°C and 15 psi for 15min. The vacuum filtered palm oil was used and the vapour-phase culturing technique was adopted by soaking the sterile Whatman filter paper no1 with palm oil and aseptically placed on the cover of the petri dishes. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 hr. Yeast flora was determined by inhibiting bacterial contaminants using 1.0µg/mL chloramphenicol [15].

2.2.4. Identification of yeast isolates obtained from palm oil polluted soil

Preliminary evaluation for biochemical identification was done using the Germ tube test, and the method is described below.

- i). 0.5mL of human serum was put into a small tube
- ii). A small colony of the yeast was touched using a pasteur pipette and gently emulsified in the serum
- iii). The tube was incubated at 37°C for 4hr
- iv). A drop of the serum was then placed on a slide and was examined using a x40 objective microscope
- v). A short filamentous extension arising unilaterally from a yeast cell, with no constriction at the point of origin indicates a positive result while no filamentous extension

arising from a yeast cell or a short hyphal extension constricted at the point of origin indicates a negative result.

2.2.5 Preparation of corn steep liquor for nitrogen enrichment

- i) 200g of corn kernel was weighed out and spread in an open container
- ii) Deionized water was sprayed richly over the corn kernel, covered completely and left for 48hr at room temperature
- iii) The corn kernel was ground into powder form with a grinding machine
- iv) The resulting corn kernel powder was soaked in water in the ratio of 1:10 (wt/v)
- v) The resulting solution was sieved with a 0.2mm diameter mesh and the liquor extracted
- vi) The extracted liquor was frozen for later use during fermentation

2.2.6 Determination of the reducing sugar

Standard dilutions of the reducing sugar were placed in 7 different tubes, and 3mL of DNSA reagent was added to each of them including a blank at room temperature and plugged with cotton wool. The test tubes were placed in a boiling water bath for 15 min and cooled at room temperature. After which the absorbance of the samples was determined using a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 540 nm. The concentration of the samples were obtained using a calibration curve developed.

2.2.7 Bioethanol production from waste newspaper using Separate Hydrolysis and Fermentation (SHF) method

(a.) Pre-treatment of waste newspaper

This was carried out to loosen the fibres of the newspaper and make it easier to separate the cellulose which is a major component of newspaper. Waste newspapers were cut manually into small pieces using scissors to increase the surface area of the paper. 300g of these shreds were weighed and soaked in 500mL of distilled water for 24hr.

(b). Hydrolysis of waste newspaper

Acid solvent hydrolysis was carried out by dispensing 100 g of the pre-treated newspaper material into a 250mL Erlenmeyer flask, and

adding 200mL of sulfuric acid solvent. The mixture was placed in an autoclave at 121°C and 15psi for 15minutes [13] The pH of the mixture was adjusted by reacting with 1.0N sodium hydroxide. After adjusting the pH, the mixture was drained and the resulting sample was filtered using a vacuum filtration apparatus to obtain the hydrolysate. The material was dried in an oven and the fermentable sugar was determined using DNSA reagent method. 0.3mL of DNSA reagent (3,5-Dinitrosalicylic acid) was mixed with 0.3mL of the resulting solution. The mixture was placed in a beaker of freshly-boiled water for 10min and observed for colour change. A change in the colour from yellow to orange indicated the presence of reducing sugars.

(c.) Fermentation of the hydrolysate leading to the production of bioethanol

1.0mL of the overnight culture suspension was added to a 90% mineral salt media (MSM) before adding 10% newspaper hydrolysate in a test tube at room temperature. The setup was kept at room temperature for 7 days. The growth was monitored through assay of biomass and bioethanol production. The performance of the process was evaluated using commercial powdered yeast, and various combinations of MSM, isolated yeast, waste newspaper and corn steep liquor. The pH (6 - 8.5), fermentation time (2-14 days) and inoculum size (2 - 10 %) were used to assess the effect of the variables on the production of bioethanol and yeast biomass. The effect of mineral media (Bushnell Haas medium (BHM) and Mineral salt medium (MSM)) on the bioethanol and biomass production was assessed using 25% waste newspaper as a carbon source which was amended with different concentrations of corn steep liquor (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 %), and Pops 1 and Pops 2 yeast isolate which were found to degrade waste newspaper after 7 days in the previous experiment.

(d). Analysis of the bioethanol

The estimation of the alcohol content from the anaerobic fermentation process was carried out

using dichromate oxidation and redox titration. 20mL of the fermentation broth was pipetted into a 100mL volumetric flask and diluted to volume with distilled water. 5.0mL of the resulting mixture was pipetted into a 50mL Schott™ reagent bottle placed in an ice water, and. 25mL of the potassium dichromate solution was slowly added to it. The mixture was placed in a water bath at 60-65°C and allowed to react for 30min. A blank sample of 5mL of distilled was used and 25mL of potassium dichromate solution was slowly added and placed in a water bath. At the end of the reaction time, both samples were removed from the water bath and allowed to cool. The alcohol content was then determined by back titration using ferrous ammonium sulphate solution. 5 drops of indicator solution was added and titration was continued until the colour changed from blue-green to brown. The blank titre V_B was recorded for the blank titration and the sample titre V_S for the sample titration.

The alcohol content was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Ethanol (\% v/v)} = 25 - (25 \times \frac{V_A}{V_B}) \quad (6)$$

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Analysis of Waste Newspaper

The result of the proximate analysis of the waste newspaper as represented in Table 1 showed that the substrate had a high percentage of carbohydrate which shows that waste newspaper has a great potential to be used as a feedstock for bioethanol potential. 3.2 Isolation of yeast species from palm oil polluted soil. The yeast isolates obtained from the palm oil impacted soil were tested for their ability to degrade waste newspaper over a period of 7 days. Among the five yeast isolates, only two (Pops 1 and Pops 2) showed a potential to degrade waste newspaper as confirmed by plate hydrolysis. The result of the biochemical analysis of the yeast isolate is presented in Table 2. It shows two strains (Pops 2 and Pops 4) fermented sucrose unlike the other five. All the isolate degraded glucose and galactose, but, none of the strains fermented all the sugars (Lactose, sucrose, galactose and glucose) tested.

Table 1. Proximate composition of the waste newspaper

Parameter	Composition (%)
Ash	0.85
Moisture Content	1.34
Crude Fibre	17.56
Crude Protein	0.028
Crude Lipid	0.003
Carbohydrate	80.219

The isolates also varied in the capacity to utilize urea, with only three (Pops 1, Pops 3 and Pops 5) showing ability to utilize urea. All the isolates were placed on the genus *Saccharomyces*.

Table 2. Biochemical characteristics of yeast isolates from palm oil impacted soil

Isolate code	Lactose	Sucrose	Galactose	Glucose	Urea	Probable Genera
Pops 1	+	-	+	+	+	<i>Saccharomyces</i> sp
Pops 2	-	+	+	+	-	<i>Saccharomyces</i> sp
Pops 3	+	-	+	+	+	<i>Saccharomyces</i> sp
Pops 4	-	+	+	+	-	<i>Saccharomyces</i> sp

3.3 Bioethanol production from waste newspaper

The fermentation of the waste newspaper was carried out using different substrates combinations MSM, yeast isolate, commercial yeast (powdered yeast), corn steep liquor and waste newspaper. The result obtained are presented in Table 3, and it shows that MSM plus isolated yeast substrate gave alcohol of 9.93 % and reducing sugar of 43 mg/mL, and MSM plus powdered yeast resulted to 8.62 %

of alcohol and reducing sugar of 42 mg/mL. The less yield obtained using MSM plus powdered yeast may be attributed to the suspected inability of the yeast to withstand stressful conditions such as ethanol concentration, temperature, osmotic stress and bacterial contamination during fermentation, unlike the yeast isolate that was obtained from paper known to be ethanol-tolerant and thermotolerant [13,21]. The combination of MSM and powdered yeast gave the least fermentation products 8.62 % and 42 (mg/mL) of bioethanol and reducing sugar, respectively, probably due to the inability of the yeast to withstand stressful conditions as mentioned earlier [3]. The highest values of 13.51 % and 51 (mg/mL) for bioethanol and reducing sugar were obtained using by the combination of MSM, waste newspaper, corn steep liquor and isolated yeast, as this yeast is wild and could tolerate stressful condition [21].

Table 3. Effect of the substrate combination on the products of the fermentation of waste newspaper using yeast isolate and commercial yeast

Sample	pH	Reducing sugar (mg/mL)	% alcohol
MSM + isolated yeast	6.34	43	9.93
MSM + waste newspaper + corn steep liquor + powdered yeast	6.12	49	11.25
MSM + powdered yeast	6.57	42	8.62
MSM + waste newspaper + corn steep liquor + isolated yeast	6.42	51	13.51

3.4 Evaluation of the effects of variables on the bioethanol, biomass and reducing sugar obtained from the fermentation of waste newspaper by yeast isolate (*Saccharomyces* sp.)

(1). Effect of pH

The pH was varied from 6 - 8.5 while keeping inoculum size and carbon:nitrogen constant at ambient temperature to determine its effect on the production of bioethanol and yeast biomass from the fermentation of waste paper during 14 days fermentation of waste newspaper. The results obtained are presented in Figures 1 and 2. Figure 1 shows that the maximum amount of bioethanol (0.246 mg/mL) and that of yeast biomass (0.64 mg/mL) were obtained using a pH 7 after 8 days of fermentation. This shows that pH impacted the bioethanol and yeast biomass production, although the maximum pH range of *Saccharomyces* sp. is between 4.0 and 5.0 (Lin et al., 2012). Using high pH range of 6 - 8.5 might have resulted in the low yield of bioethanol (13.51 %) obtained, as pH above 5.0 is known to reduce the concentration of ethanol significantly [19].

Figure 1. Effect of pH on the production of bioethanol from waste newspaper by the *Saccharomyces* sp. during 14 days fermentation of waste newspaper

The yield of the bioethanol and yeast biomass as shown in Figures 1 and 2, dropped beyond 8 days of fermentation. This could be due to the toxic effect of the high concentration of ethanol which was suspected on a prolong fermentation time beyond 8 days. Although, longer fermentation time was required to achieve a completion fermentation of the waste newspaper at an ambient temperature, but, it is usually accompanied by lowest yield of bioethanol [22].

Figure 2. Effect of pH on the production of yeast biomass by the *Saccharomyces* sp. during 14 days fermentation of waste newspaper

(2). Effect of the inoculum size

This was assessed by varying the inoculum size between 2 and 10 % while keeping other parameters such as pH, and temperature constant during the fermentation of waste newspaper by yeast isolate for a period of 14 days. The results of the bioethanol and yeast biomass obtained are presented in Figures 3 and 4. The result shows that the maximum bioethanol (0.27 mg/mL) and yeast biomass (0.60 mg/mL) were obtained using an inoculum size of 6 % after 8 days of incubation. Beyond the inoculum size of 6%, increase in the inoculum size will reduce the production of ethanol as the nutrients begin to deplete [9].

Figure 3. Effect of inoculation size on the production of bioethanol by the *Saccharomyces* sp. during 14 days fermentation of waste newspaper

Figure 4. Effect of inoculation size on the production of yeast biomass by the *Saccharomyces* sp. during 14 days fermentation of waste newspaper

(3). Effect of nutrients combination

This helped to determine the effect of carbon:nitrogen ratio on the production of bioethanol and yeast biomass from the fermentation of waste newspaper by yeast isolates (Pops 1 and 2). The effect was evaluated using two different media namely: Bushnell Haas medium (BHM) and Mineral salt medium (MSM) comprising 25% paper as the sole carbon source which was amended with different concentrations of corn steep liquor (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 %) used as nitrogen source. The results obtained are presented in Figures 5 and 6. Figure 5 shows that the medium comprising MSM with 25% paper as sole carbon source and 2% corn steep liquor gave the maximum bioethanol yield (24.2 mg/mL) when fermented with yeast isolate Pops 1 after a fermentation time of 14 days. This amounted to a carbon/nitrogen ratio of 25:2. Similarly, the medium consisting MSM, 25 % waste newspaper and 0.1 % corn steep liquor gave the optimum yeast biomass of 0.6 mg/mL using yeast isolate Pops 2 (Figure 6). The carbon:nitrogen ratio was 25/0.1.

Figure 5. Effect of substrate combinations on the production of bioethanol by two yeast isolate (Pops 1 and Pops 2) during 14 days fermentation of waste newspaper

Figure 6. Effect of substrate combinations on the production of yeast biomass by two yeast isolate (Pops 1 and Pops 2) during 14 days fermentation of waste newspaper

3.4 Analysis of bioethanol produced from waste newspaper using yeast isolate from palm oil polluted soil

The physicochemical properties of the bioethanol was analysed and the result obtained is presented in Table 4. The properties are in agreement with those obtained from the literature. The disparities in the values of the properties may be attributed to the presence of water in the bioethanol distillate due to the azeotrope between ethanol and water [16].

Table 4. Physicochemical properties of bioethanol

Sample	Bioethanol	Bioethanol	Ref.
	(current work)	(Literature)	
Density (g/ml)	0.776	0.79	Avinash and Sasikumar (2016) [2]
Kinematic Viscosity @40°C (mPa.s ⁻¹)	1.274	1.2	Avinash and Sasikumar (2016)[2]
Oxygen content (%)	34.78	34.7	Avinash and Sasikumar (2016)[2]
Cetane number	6.4	6	Avinash and Sasikumar (2016)[2]
Latent Heat of Vaporization (MJ/kg)	0.58	0.91	Khuong et al. (2016)[11]
Calorific Value (MJ/kg)	21.96	25.22, 26.70	Khuong et al. (2016)[11]
Flash Point (°C)	19.5	19	Tadmourt et al. (2020)[20]
Ignition Temp. (°C)	310.8	332.8, 366.0	Battelle (1998)[4]
Octane number/MON	84.2	92	Yucesu et al. (2006)[24]
Water Content	7.48%	2024 mg/kg	Khuong et al. (2016)[16]

4.0 Conclusion

It has been demonstrated that bioethanol can be produced from the fermentation of waste papers using yeast isolated from palm oil polluted soil. All the yeast isolates tested positive for fermenting galactose and glucose,

but, showed variability in degrading lactose, and sucrose. Despite this, the yeast isolate (pops 1) using MSM, 25 % waste newspaper and 2 % corn steep liquor gave the highest concentration of bioethanol of 24.2 mg/mL after 14 days of fermentation. The physicochemical properties compared

favorably well with the standards references. Considering the high carbohydrate content of the waste papers (80.2 %) and its abundance, and the potency of the yeast isolates, the method developed can be used to support bioethanol production and could help to ensure sustainable management of waste papers through valorization.

References

1. Aduloju, B. (2021). Nigeria Puts the Brakes on Ambitious Biofuels Refinery Plan. Africa Oil + gas report, April 9, 2021. <https://africaoilgasreport.com/2021/04/energy-transition/nigeria-puts-the-brakes-on-ambitious-biofuels-refinery-plan/>
2. Avinash, A. and Sasikumar, P. (2016). A comprehensive study on the emission characteristics of E-diesel dual-fuel engine. Alexandria Engineering Journal, 55(1):351-356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2015.10.002>
3. Basso, L. C., Amorim, H. V., Oliveira, A. J., Lopes, M. L. (2008). Yeast selection for fuel ethanol production in Brazil, FEMS Yeast Res. 8:1155–1163
4. Battelle, P. A., (1998). Flammability limits for ethanol/diesel blends. Final Report prepared by Battelle, Columbus, OH, USA
5. Brummer, V., Jurena, T., Hlavacek, V., Omelkova, J., Bebar, L., Gabriel, P., Stehlik, P. (2014). Enzymatic hydrolysis of pretreated waste paper – source of raw material for production of liquid biofuels. Bioresour. Technol. 152, 543–547.
6. Dien, B. S., Cotta, M. A., Jeffries, T. W. (2003). Bacteria engineered for fuel ethanol production: current status, Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol. 63: 258–266.
7. Dubey, A.K., Gupta, P.K., Garg, N., Naithani, S. (2012). Bioethanol production from waste paper acid pretreated hydrolysate with xylose fermenting *Pichia stipitis*. Carbohydr. Polym. 88, 825–829.
8. Effiong, E., Agwa, O. K., & Abu, G. O. (2019). Optimization of Biosurfactant production by a novel Rhizobacterial *Pseudomonas* species. *World Scientific News*, 137, 18-30.
9. Hosny, M., Abo-State, M. A., El-Temtamy, S. A., El-Sheikh, H. H. (2016). Factors Affecting Bioethanol Production from Hydrolyzed Bagasse, Int. J. Adv. Res. Biol. Sci, 3(9):130-138
10. [10]. Kasavi, C., Finore, I., Lama, L., et al., (2012). Evaluation of industrial *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* strains for ethanol production from biomass, Biomass- Bioenergy 45: 230–238.
11. Khuong, L. S., Zulkifli, N. W. M., Masjuki, H. H., Mohamad, E. N., Arslan, A., Mosarof, M. H., Azham, A. (2016). A review on the effect of bioethanol dilution on the properties and performance of automotive lubricants in gasoline engines. RSC Adv. 6, 66847-66869
12. Lin, Y., Zhang, W., Li, C., et al. (2012). Factors affecting ethanol fermentation using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* BY4742, Biomass- Bioenergy 47: 395–401.
13. Manna, M. S., Bhowmick, T. K., Gayen, K. (2020). Acid hydrolysis of the waste newspaper: Comparison of process variables for finding the best condition to produce quality fermentable sugars, Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2020.104345>
14. OECD (2022). OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2021-2030, <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/89d2ac54-en/index.html?itemId=/content/component/89d2ac54-en>
15. Orhorhoro, E., Effiong, E., & Abu, G. (2018). Laboratory-scale bioremediation of crude oil polluted soil using a consortium of rhizobacteria obtained from plants in Gokana-Ogoni, Rivers State. *Journal of Advanced Microbiology*, 9, 1-17.
16. Tadmourt, W., Khiari, K., Boulal, A., Tarabet, L. (2022). Waste paper valorization for bioethanol production. Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery,

- Utilization, and Environmental Effects. DOI: 10.1080/15567036.2020.1815908
17. Rahman, M.O., Hussain, A., Basri, H., (2014). A critical review on waste paper sorting techniques. *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 11, 551–564.
18. Shi, A.Z., Koh, L.P., Tan, H.T.W., (2009). The biofuel potential of municipal solid waste. *GCB Bioenergy* 1, 317–320.
19. Staniszewski, M., Kujawski, W., Lewandowska, M. (2007). Ethanol production from whey in bioreactor with co-immobilized enzyme and yeast cells followed by pervaporative recovery of product – Kinetic model predictions, *J. Food Eng.* 82: 618–625.
20. Tadmourt, W., Khiari, K., Boulal, A., Trabet, L. (2020). Waste paper valorization for bioethanol production: Pretreatment and acid hydrolysis optimization, *Energy Source*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15567036.2020.1815908>
21. Tofighi, A., Assadi, M. M., Asadirad, M. H. A., Karizi, S. Z. (2014). Bio-ethanol production by a novel autochthonous thermo-tolerant yeast isolated from wastewater, *J. Environ. Health Sci. Eng.* 12:107.
22. Zabed, H., Faruq, G., Sahu, J. N., et al., (2014). Bioethanol production from fermentable sugar juice, *Sci. World J.*, 1–11.
23. Zhang, Z.R., Macquarrie, D.J., De Bruyn, M., Budarin, V.L., Hunt, A.J., Gronnow, M.J., Fan, J.J., Shuttleworth, P.S., Clark, J.H., Matharu, A.S., 2015. Low-temperature microwave-assisted pyrolysis of waste office paper and the application of biooil as an AI adhesive. *Green Chem.* 17, 260–270.
24. Yucesu, H. S., Topgul, T. T., Cinar, C., Okur, M. (2006). Effect of ethanol-gasoline blends on engine performance and exhaust emission in different compression ratios, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 26, 2272 - 2272 - 2278